

Cultural Heritage as FAIR Digital Object?

3D-Erfassung und semantische Vernetzung von Kulturerbe in Irland und Schottland

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3D Tage | 2026 | 25-26 Feb 2026 | Dresden | Germany | 26/02/2026

Themenblock: AG3D

image: Florian Thiery CC BY 4.0, created using OpenAI's DALLE

via <https://www.w3.org/DesignIssues/LinkedData.html>

Linked Open Data (LOD) is the method of choice for linking data and FAIRification ...

... to feed the federated Knowledge Graph Ecosystem.

FAIR access to 3D data plays a crucial role in fostering transparency, reproducibility, and community engagement

How can 3D models be described, identified and integrated into the Federated Knowledge Ecosystem as FAIR Digital Objects (FDOs)?

Which (Meta-)Data Standards can help to integrate 3D models as FDOs into interdisciplinary graphs?

GeoSPARQL

CIDOC CRM

CFF

DCAT

LOD

Wikibase

FAIR Digital Object

Data

Metadata

PID

The mix of Linked Open Data (RDF), Wikibase instances, and FAIR Digital Objects may help!

image: Florian Thiery CC BY 4.0, created using OpenAI's DALL-E

<https://squirrelbase.wikibase.cloud>

via <https://squirrelbase.wikibase.cloud/entity/Q22>

Item **Discussion**

CIIC 81 / UCC 4 / CO074-148---- (Q48)

No description defined

In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	CIIC 81 / UCC 4 / CO074-148----	No description defined	
German	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	
default for all languages	No label defined	--	

Statements

instance of **Q** Object

↳ 0 references

Wikidata Q-ID **Q** Q130529871

↳ 0 references

OSM ID **Q** node/11071361392

↳ 0 references

representative point **Q** 51°53'37.3740"N, 8°29'32.7149"W

↳ 0 references

via <https://tjp.de/Oale3>

item	itemLabel	geo
Q130529871	Alderstein Grenzstein (Aachen)	Point(6.0187331 50.7617299)
Q48	Asymmetrische Vase (Berlin Kuddamm)	Point(13.3249878 52.5026745)
Q25	Alderstein in Vaals (Niederlande)	Point(6.0187331 50.7617299)
Q65	Rom Capitol Kopf Konstantin	Point(12.482334 41.892906)
Q27	Rom Capitol Hand Konstantin	Point(12.4823388 41.892906111)
Q8	Rom Capitol Fuß Konstantin	Point(12.4823388 41.892906111)
Q2	Berliner Siegestsäule (Mosaik)	Point(13.300108 52.514512)
Q10	Der "Große Sitzender" (Dom Würzburg)	Point(9.9318653 49.7936363)
Q11	Gedenkstein von Kurtarlst Karl (Schloss Heidelberg)	Point(8.714044 49.410568)
Q12	Vater Rhein (Schloss Heidelberg)	Point(8.7191369 49.4102478)
Q13	Domnagel (Speyer)	Point(8.441199 49.317267)
Q14	Geißbockbrunnen (Deidesheim)	Point(8.190597 49.407566)
Q15	Köln Hohenzollernbrücke (Schlosser)	Point(6.965944 50.941421)
Q16	Statua del Mendicante di Anterselva	Point(12.1679203 46.6825371)
Q22	Milestone Maudlin Street (Kilkenny)	Point(-7.2442662 52.6526592)
Q153	CIIC 153	Point(9.6430769 52.2786257)

The **Squirrel Base** can provide FAIR metadata for 3D objects!

LOD

Wikibase

FDO

GIS

OSM

LPG

HIN

EpiDoc

How to “feed” the **Federated Knowledge Graph Ecosystem**?

Ogham Stones

3D-Modelle in der LOD Cloud

Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)

(C) OpenStreetMap contributors
Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

image: Florian Thiery CC BY 4.0, created using OpenAI's DALL-E

Florian Thiery & Peter Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Ogham! 4.-6. AD, early Medieval, “Primitive Irish”

This project is funded by Wikimedia Deutschland e. V. within the Open Science Fellows Program.

Ogham Stones im Federated Knowledge Graph Ecosystem

SfM-Kampagne mit der KIRI Engine App

Ogham Stone GEARS/1 im Cork Public Museum

Ogham Stones CHUIS/1 in 3DHOP via archaeosquirrels.cloud

Item [Discussion](#)

CHUIS/1 (Q25)

object

[In more languages](#)
Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	CHUIS/1	object
German	No label defined	No description defined
American English	No label defined	No description defined
default for all languages	No label defined	—

Statements

[instance of](#) Object
0 references

[Wikidata Q-ID](#) Q126500897
0 references

[OSM ID](#) node/11966430251
0 references

[representative point](#) 51°53′45.9172″N, 8°29′39.5318″W
0 references

aligned with term

<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q2016147>

alignment label	Ogham Stone
alignment type (SKOS)	skos:exactMatch
alignment score	7 Star
alignment repository	Wikidata
alignment description	object type
alignment source	FDO

0 references

<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q24041450>

alignment label	Cork Public Museum
alignment type (SKOS)	skos:relatedMatch
alignment score	3 Star
alignment repository	Wikidata
alignment description	exhibition
alignment source	FDO

0 references

CHUIS/1 in der SquirrelBase I

[Main page](#)
[Recent changes](#)
[Random page](#)
[Help about MediaWiki](#)

[Tools](#)
[What links here](#)
[Related changes](#)
[Special pages](#)
[Printable version](#)
[Permanent link](#)
[Page information](#)
[Concept URI](#)

[Wikibase](#)
[New Item](#)
[New Property](#)
[New Schema](#)
[All Properties](#)
[Query Service](#)
[Cradle](#)
[QuickStatements](#)

[In other languages](#)
[Add links](#)

KIRI URL

<https://www.kiriengine.app/share/shareModel/3d5e669d143540319070d449ef50092f>

acquisition method	Structure from Motion (SfM)
acquisition hardware	Samsung Galaxy S22
acquisition software	KIRI engine
acquisition creator	Florian Thiery
acquisition license	CC BY-SA 4.0

▼ 0 references

3DHOP URL

http://archaeosquirrels.cloud/?model=CHUIS_1

acquisition method	Structure from Motion (SfM)
acquisition hardware	Samsung Galaxy S22
acquisition software	KIRI engine
acquisition creator	Florian Thiery
acquisition license	CC BY-SA 4.0

▼ 0 references

Sketchfab URL

<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/cork-public-museum-chuis1-07d2bad6bbeb45d99fac246462af6eba>

acquisition method	Structure from Motion (SfM)
acquisition hardware	Samsung Galaxy S22
acquisition software	KIRI engine
acquisition creator	Florian Thiery
acquisition license	CC BY-SA 4.0

▼ 0 references

3D File URL

https://ogham.celt.dias.ie/version2013/stone.php?lang=en&site=Cork_Public_Museum&stone=Church_Island&stoneinfo=inscription

acquisition method	Laser Scan
acquisition hardware	Artec Eva scanner
acquisition software	Geomagic
acquisition creator	Gary Devlin, Discovery Programme
acquisition license	CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 Ireland

▼ 0 references

CHUIS/1 in der SquirrelBase II

FDO URL

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18369720>

FDO type fdo:3DDataFDO

FDO format glb

ply

nxs

nxz

FDO license CC BY-SA 4.0

FDO release version v0.3.1

▼ 0 references

CHUIS/1 in der SquirrelBase III

MD.cff

Semantic metadata from MD.cff — title, spatial/temporal extent, heritage object properties, technique.

Field	Value
agent.publisher	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q73981970
dataset.date_created	2024-06-06
dataset.date_modified	2024-06-19
dataset.date_released	2024-06-09
dataset.description	Ogham Stone CHUIS/1 located in the Cork Public Museum
dataset.funding	Community Project
dataset.heritage_object.conservancy_urgency	low
dataset.heritage_object.context	Ogham Stones in the Wild and in Museums in Ireland bearing Ogham inscriptions.
dataset.heritage_object.documentation_purpose	make 3d model available
dataset.heritage_object.material	{'label': 'Stone', 'id': 'http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q22731'}
dataset.heritage_object.object_type	{'label': 'Inscribed Ogham stone', 'id': 'http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q2016147'}
dataset.heritage_object.overall_condition	good
dataset.id	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18369720
dataset.license	https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-SA-4.0.html
dataset.publisher	Research Squirrel Engineers Network
dataset.spatial.geometry	sf:Point
dataset.spatial.id	https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/11966430251
dataset.technique.processing	{'software': 'KIRI Engine', 'steps': 'Take photos, align photos; build dense cloud; generate mesh; texture; export.'}
dataset.temporal	http://chronontology.dainst.org/period/aChcHZd1Bhkt
dataset.temporal.id	http://chronontology.dainst.org/period/aChcHZd1Bhkt
dataset.title	CHUIS/1
dataset.version	1.0

CITATION.cff

Citation metadata from CITATION.cff — creators, license, keywords.

Field	Value
agent.creator	Thiery, Florian
dataset.creators	Thiery, Florian
keywords	"Cork Public Museum"
keywords (DCAT/DC added)	Cork Public Museum
license	"CC-BY-SA-4.0"
license (SPDX URI added)	https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-SA-4.0.html
subject	"Cork Public Museum"

CHUIS/1 - MD.cff und CITATION.cff

```

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18369720> a dcat:Dataset, crmdig:D1, crm:E73, fdo:3DDataF00 ;
  dct:description "Ogham Stone CHUIS/1 located in the Cork Public Museum" ;
  dct:hasVersion "1.0" ;
  dct:creator <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3246-3531> ;
  dct:license <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-SA-4.0.html> ;
  dct:publisher <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q73901970> ;
  dct:title "CHUIS/1" ;
  dcat:keyword <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q2016147>,
    "Ogham Stone",
    <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q24041450>,
    "Cork Public Museum" ;
  dct:subject <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q2016147>,
    "Ogham Stone",
    <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q24041450>,
    "Cork Public Museum" ;
  dcat:distribution <urn:fdo-squirrel:dist/a38bdba40d281c5f>,
    <urn:fdo-squirrel:dist/ad106454448bfc9b>,
    <urn:fdo-squirrel:dist/e8b0736ae7265071>,
    <urn:fdo-squirrel:dist/23b0e534f5a9b40f>,
    <urn:fdo-squirrel:dist/1ffe5e794229db4f>,
    <urn:fdo-squirrel:dist/12e586334338f44a>,
    <urn:fdo-squirrel:dist/6acdb6353bc97f82> ;
  dct:created "2024-06-06"^^xsd:date ;
  dct:issued "2024-06-09"^^xsd:date ;
  dct:modified "2024-06-19"^^xsd:date ;
  schema:funding "Community Project" ;
  dct:spatial <https://www.openstreetmap.org/node/11966430251> ;
  schema:latitude "51.8961"^^xsd:decimal ;
  schema:longitude "-8.4943"^^xsd:decimal ;
  fdo:context "Ogham Stones in the Wild and in Museums in Ireland bearing Ogham inscriptions." ;
  dct:type <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q2016147> ;
  dct:subject <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q22731> ;
  dct:description "make 3d model available" ;
  dct:description "good" ;
  dct:description "low" ;
  dct:provenance "{ \"software\": \"KIRI Engine\", \"steps\": \"Take photos, align photos; build dense cloud; generate mesh; texture; export.\"} " .

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18369720> geosparql:hasGeometry <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18369720_geom> .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18369720_geom> a sf:Point .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18369720_geom> geosparql:asWKT "<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326> POINT(-8.4943 51.8961)"^^geosparql:wktLiteral .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18369720> dct:temporal <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18369720_temporal> .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18369720_temporal> a dct:PeriodOfTime .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18369720_temporal> rdfs:label "Ogham stone inscriptions (ca. 4th-7th century CE)" .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18369720_temporal> dcat:startDate "300"^^xsd:integer .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18369720_temporal> dcat:endDate "699"^^xsd:integer .

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18369720> cff:keywords "Cork Public Museum" .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18369720> cff:keywords "Ogham Stone" .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18369720> cff:license "CC-BY-SA-4.0" .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18369720> cff:license <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-SA-4.0.html> .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18369720> cff:license-url "CC-BY-SA-4.0" .
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18369720> cff:license-url <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-SA-4.0.html> .
codemeta:keywords "Cork Public Museum" .
codemeta:keywords "Ogham Stone" .
codemeta:license "CC-BY-SA-4.0" .
codemeta:license <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-SA-4.0.html> .
dcat:keyword "Cork Public Museum" .
dcat:keyword "Ogham Stone" .
dct:license <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-SA-4.0.html> .
dct:subject "Cork Public Museum" .
dct:subject "Ogham Stone" .
schema:description "Ogham Stone CHUIS/1 located in the Cork Public Museum" .
schema:keywords "Cork Public Museum" .
schema:keywords "Ogham Stone" .
schema:license "CC-BY-SA-4.0" .
schema:license <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-SA-4.0.html> .
wdt:P275 "CC-BY-SA-4.0" .
wdt:P275 <https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-SA-4.0.html> .
wdt:P921 "Cork Public Museum" .
wdt:P921 "Ogham Stone" .

<https://spdx.org/licenses/CC-BY-SA-4.0.html> rdfs:label "CC-BY-SA-4.0" .

```

CHUIS/1 - FDO-RDF

ZIP — Distributions (10 files)

Each file in the ZIP becomes a `dcnat:Distribution`. All properties below are written into the TTL.

fd:path	fd:role	mediaType	byteSize	sha256 (prefix)
CHUIS_1.jpg	documentation	image/jpeg	1453939	a38bdba40d281c5f
CHUIS_1.nxs	model	application/octet-stream	77169408	ad106454448bfc9b
CHUIS_1.nxz	model	application/octet-stream	18801920	e8b0736ae7265071
CHUIS_1.ply	model	application/octet-stream	95846610	23b0e534f5a9b40f
CITATION.cff	metadata	text/yaml	253	1ffe5e794229db4f
cork_public_museum_chuis1.glb	model	model/gltf-binary	56819948	12e586334338f444
fd-metadatas.ttl	data	application/octet-stream	8318	f54cceb345af74e3
MD.cff	metadata	text/yaml	2178	6acd6353bc97f82
rdf_modelling_report.html	data	text/html	16747	6605246a5cfcf03ba
rdf_modelling_report.json	documentation	application/json	13587	1c2b731ee72334c

```
<urn:fd-squirrel:dist/a38bdba40d281c5f> a dcat:Distribution, crmdig:D9 ;
  dcat:accessURL <urn:fd-squirrel:content/CHUIS_1.jpg> ;
  dcat:byteSize 1453939 ;
  dcat:mediaType "image/jpeg" ;
  fd:path "CHUIS_1.jpg" ;
  fd:role "documentation" ;
  fd:sha256 "a38bdba40d281c5f0237a2f350ba32abe19863974d6fdc972d1bb0c1232d5155" .

<urn:fd-squirrel:dist/ad106454448bfc9b> a dcat:Distribution, crmdig:D9 ;
  dcat:accessURL <urn:fd-squirrel:content/CHUIS_1.nxs> ;
  dcat:byteSize 77169408 ;
  dcat:mediaType "application/octet-stream" ;
  fd:path "CHUIS_1.nxs" ;
  fd:role "data" ;
  fd:sha256 "ad106454448bfc9b3a31e4151c7d99b9f90eda0c50ce4f7d6cd193e7ceba314f" .

<urn:fd-squirrel:dist/e8b0736ae7265071> a dcat:Distribution, crmdig:D9 ;
  dcat:accessURL <urn:fd-squirrel:content/CHUIS_1.nxz> ;
  dcat:byteSize 18801920 ;
  dcat:mediaType "application/octet-stream" ;
  fd:path "CHUIS_1.nxz" ;
  fd:role "data" ;
  fd:sha256 "e8b0736ae7265071bfff4284129ab01a97aalb473e603a62e395057a47f43857" .

<urn:fd-squirrel:dist/23b0e534f5a9b40f> a dcat:Distribution, crmdig:D9 ;
  dcat:accessURL <urn:fd-squirrel:content/CHUIS_1.ply> ;
  dcat:byteSize 95846610 ;
  dcat:mediaType "application/octet-stream" ;
  fd:path "CHUIS_1.ply" ;
  fd:role "model" ;
  fd:sha256 "23b0e534f5a9b40f21cfceeda0a2008b0601173a55a7507c3e386fd115bfa0" .

<urn:fd-squirrel:dist/1ffe5e794229db4f> a dcat:Distribution, crmdig:D9 ;
  dcat:accessURL <urn:fd-squirrel:content/CITATION.cff> ;
  dcat:byteSize 253 ;
  dcat:mediaType "text/yaml" ;
  fd:path "CITATION.cff" ;
  fd:role "data" ;
  fd:sha256 "1ffe5e794229db4fcd6f7b9974a176d59c0d9001f8d1a5ea762c85a800fe17a9" .

<urn:fd-squirrel:dist/12e586334338f444> a dcat:Distribution, crmdig:D9 ;
  dcat:accessURL <urn:fd-squirrel:content/cork_public_museum_chuis1.glb> ;
  dcat:byteSize 56819948 ;
  dcat:mediaType "model/gltf-binary" ;
  fd:path "cork_public_museum_chuis1.glb" ;
  fd:role "model" ;
  fd:sha256 "12e586334338f44421d20d8bd5d2d8eabe61c0fbb7222560c552ba7e40602b61" .

<urn:fd-squirrel:dist/6acd6353bc97f82> a dcat:Distribution, crmdig:D9 ;
  dcat:accessURL <urn:fd-squirrel:content/MD.cff> ;
  dcat:byteSize 2178 ;
  dcat:mediaType "text/yaml" ;
  fd:path "MD.cff" ;
  fd:role "data" ;
  fd:sha256 "6acd6353bc97f8213fda5eccddc6f0af9a7668332e99823e27c5a1994b6434" .
```

CHUIS/1 - ZIP Distributions

CIIC 81

- **UCC Cork Stone Corridor: #4**
- **OSM Node: 11071361392**
- **Wikidata: Q130529871**

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

Knoten: CIIC 81 /
UCC 4 (11071361392)

Version #2

added metadata

Bearbeitet vor 19 Tagen von fthiergyeo

Änderungssatz #139090380

Standort: 51.8938126, -8.4921198

Tags

historic	ogham_stone
inscription	C[A]J[S]I[T]T[A]O]S MAQI MU[CO]I CALLITI
moved	yes
moved_to	Q69379477
name	CIIC 81 / UCC 4
project	ogham.link
source	survey
wikidata	Q106680733

Florian Thieri, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

Cork: Ogham stone CIIC 81/ UCC 4
3D Model

b-unicycling
FOLLOWING

UCC Ogham Stone #4 in Sketchfab

UCC Ogham Stone #4 in 3DHOP via archaeosquirrels.cloud

Item **Discussion**

CIIC 81 / UCC 4 / CO074-148---- (Q48)

No description defined

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	CIIC 81 / UCC 4 / CO074-148---	No description defined
German	No label defined	No description defined
American English	No label defined	No description defined
default for all languages	No label defined	—

Statements

Instance of	Object	▼ 0 references
Wikidata Q-ID	Q130529871	▼ 0 references
OSM ID	node/11071361392	▼ 0 references
representative point	51°53′37.3740″N, 8°29′32.7149″W	▼ 0 references

aligned with term

 <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q2016147>

alignment label	Ogham Stone
alignment type (SKOS)	skos:exactMatch
alignment score	7 Star
alignment repository	Wikidata
alignment description	object type
alignment source	FDO

▼ 0 references

 <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q121592049>

alignment label	UCC Stone Corridor
alignment type (SKOS)	skos:relatedMatch
alignment score	3 Star
alignment repository	Wikidata
alignment description	exhibition
alignment source	FDO

▼ 0 references

UCC Ogham Stone #4 in der SquirrelBase I

Main page
Recent changes
Random page
Help about MediaWiki

Tools
What links here
Related changes
Special pages
Printable version
Permanent link
Page information
Concept URI

Wikibase
New Item
New Property
New Schema
All Properties
Query Service
Cradle
QuickStatements

In other languages
Add links

3DHOP URL

<http://archaeosquirrels.cloud/?model=CO074-148---->

acquisition method	Structure from Motion (SfM)
acquisition hardware	iPhone
acquisition software	KIRI engine
acquisition creator	Anne-Karoline Distel
acquisition license	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

▼ 0 references

Sketchfab URL

<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/cork-ogham-stone-ciic-81-ucc-4-4cb26986be274ee099515c2baa3b1825>

acquisition method	Structure from Motion (SfM)
acquisition hardware	iPhone
acquisition software	KIRI engine
acquisition creator	Anne-Karoline Distel
acquisition license	CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

▼ 0 references

UCC Ogham Stone #4 in der SquirrelBase II

FDO URL

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18724635>

FDO type fdo:3DDataFDO

FDO format glb

ply

nxs

nxz

FDO license CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

FDO release version v0.3.1

▼ 0 references

UCC Ogham Stone #4 in der SquirrelBase III

- *Analogue Sources: CIIC, CISP*
- *Linked Open Ogham Data: providing the primary URI*
 - http://lod.ogham.link/data/OghamStone_Squirrel_collection
- *fuzzy-sl Wikibase: coordinates and how they are created*
 - [P4](#)
- *Wikidata: data-hub for external identifiers, e.g., OSM, SMRS, LOD*
 - [P11693](#), [P4057](#), [P2888](#)
- *Semantic Kompakkt Wikibase: 3D Model & Annotations*
 - [P74](#), [P75](#)
- *FactGrid Wikibase for Historians: Inscription & Persons & Words*
 - [P1219](#), [P33](#), [P256](#)
- *TEI/EpiDOC (from the OG(H)AM project)*
- *Open Street Map*
 - [historic=ogham_stone](#)

Use each Repository for data it is “famous” for ...

Ausführen Teilen Export Wizard Speichern Laden Einstellungen Hilfe **overpass turbo** Karte Daten

```

1 /*
2 This is an example Overpass query.
3 Try it out by pressing the Run button above!
4 You can find more examples with the Load tool.
5 */
6 node
7   [historic=ogham_stone]
8   {{{bbox}}};
9 out;

```

```

<node id="5145413640" lat="52.1102476" lon="-10.4731913">
  <tag k="historic" v="ogham_stone"/>
  <tag k="inscription" v="ERC MAQI MAQI-ERCIAS MU DOVINIA"/>
  <tag k="moved" v="no"/>
  <tag k="name" v="CIIC 178"/>
  <tag k="project" v="ogham.link"/>
  <tag k="ref:IE:smr" v="KE052-059002-"/>
  <tag k="source" v="survey"/>
  <tag k="wikidata" v="Q70892682"/>
  <tag k="wikimedia_commons" v="File:Coumeenoole_Ogham_Stone_(Dunmore_Head).jpg"/>
</node>

```

Node 5145413640

Tags

- historic = ogham_stone
- inscription = ERC MAQI MAQI-ERCIAS MU DOVINIA
- moved = no
- name = CIIC 178
- project = ogham.link
- ref:IE:smr = KE052-059002-
- source = survey
- wikidata = Q70892682
- wikimedia_commons = File:Coumeenoole_Ogham_Stone_(Dunmore_Head).jpg

Coordinates:
52.1102476 / -10.4731913 (latlon)

geladen – Nodes: 7, Ways: 0, Relations: 0
angezeigt – POIs: 7, Linien: 0, Polygone: 0

Leaflet | © OpenStreetMap contributors
geladen – Nodes: 106, Ways: 0, Relations: 0
angezeigt – POIs: 106, Linien: 0, Polygone: 0

via <https://overpass-turbo.eu/s/1lwq>

Florian Thierry, CC BY 4.0, via [Wikimedia Commons](#)

OpenStreetMap [Overpass-Turbo]

Item Discussion

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q74)

Ogham Stone #4 UCC Stone Corridor at UCC Cork

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Ogham Stone #4 UCC Stone Corridor at UCC Cork	

Statements

instance of	Archaeological Site	→ 0 references
related to	http://wikidata.org/entity/Q130529671 related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch → 0 references	
related to	https://wikibase.semantic-kompaakt.de/entity/Q1247 related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch → 0 references	
related to	https://database.bartnrd.de/entity/Q1000294 related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch → 0 references	
related to	http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y00000081 related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch → 0 references	

Florian Thiery, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0

via <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q74>

has coordinate

51°53'37.3"N, 8°29'32.6"W

certainty level High

certainty description on-site survey at exhibition area

method used on-site survey

acting person Florian Thiery

source type (detail) on-site survey (source type)

source type (generic) on-site survey (source type)

method description on-site survey at UCC Cork

precision ±0.0001°

location type Exhibition Site

point type Exhibition

→ 0 references

51°48'59.58"N, 8°45'57.13"W

certainty level

certainty description

Low

method used

acting person

source type (generic)

source type (detail)

method description

precision

location type

point type

Gippert/Web, Ogham 81:
 "According to Brash, JRSAI 10, 1869, 260, the stone was found in a structure called Rath Lisheenagreine, in the townland of Gurrans (sic!), parish of Templemartin, 1 mile. north of the parish church (the village in question is named "Gurrans" in the Cork U.C. too). A detailed map of the rath (in connection with the larger Rath Lisnacaheragh) is available in S.P. O' R'Yordain's article in PRIA 47-C, 1941-42, 77 ff. - According to Brash, the stone was discovered by one farmer Crowley 17 years before (the publication of his article in JRSAI 10, 1869); Macalister states in CIIC that it "has been known since the sixties" and "appears to have come from a souterrain in the group" of "earth-works" on the townland of Gurrans. The first report was made by John Lyons, C.C., Newcestown, Enniskeane; Brash's visit took place on 16.12.1868. The stone was moved to the Museum of the U.C., Cork after Macalister first visited it (at that time it was still "standing loosely in one of the ditches": CIIC 1, 84). In the collection of the U.C., it is assigned no. 17."

Georeferencing

Florian Thiery

Textual Description

Paper

found in old documents

±0.0001°

Findspot

Location of a Place as a Concept

Define SPARQL query service

```
import os
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
import pandas as pd
import geopandas as gpd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from shapely.geometry import Point
import contextily as ctx # For adding OpenStreetMap basemaps
from matplotlib.patches import Patch
from scipy.stats import gaussian_kde
import numpy as np

def querySparql(query):
    sparql = SPARQLWrapper("https://query.wikidata.org/sparql")
    sparql.setQuery(query)
    sparql.setReturnFormat(JSON)
    results = sparql.queryAndConvert()
    return results['results']['bindings']

# Define the GeoJSON file path
geojson_file = os.path.join(os.getcwd(), "gs_ireland_island.geojson") # Adjusted for Jupyter
```

Define the SPARQL Query

```
# SPARQL Query
oghamQuery = """
SELECT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo ?site ?siteLabel ?county ?countyLabel WHERE {
  ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q3816147.
  ?item wdt:P189 ?site.
  ?site wdt:P31 wd:Q72617871.
  ?item wdt:P189 ?county.
  ?county wdt:P31 wd:Q179872.
  ?item wdt:P625 ?geo.
  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en." }
}
"""
```

Fetch Data and Convert to DataFrame

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(oghamQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []
for result in sparql_results:
    geo = result['geo']['value'] if 'geo' in result else None
    lat, lon = (None, None)
    if geo:
        lon, lat = map(float, geo.replace("Point(", "").replace(")", "").split(","))
    data.append({
        "item": result['item']['value'],
        "itemLabel": result['itemLabel']['value'],
        "site": result['site']['value'],
        "siteLabel": result['siteLabel']['value'],
        "county": result['county']['value'],
        "countyLabel": result['countyLabel']['value'],
        "latitude": lat,
        "longitude": lon,
    })

df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df
```

Visualise the Data as Maps

```
# Check if DataFrame is populated
if df.empty:
    print("No data retrieved from the query.")
else:
    # Filter rows with valid coordinates
    df_with_coords = df.dropna(subset=['latitude', 'longitude'])

    # Create a GeoDataFrame
    gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(
        df_with_coords,
        geometry=[Point(xy) for xy in zip(df_with_coords['longitude'], df_with_coords['latitude'])],
        crs="EPSG:4326"
    )

    # Convert to Web Mercator for OSM basemap
    gdf_mercator = gdf.to_crs(epsg=3857)

    # Load Ireland boundary from GeoJSON
    ireland_boundary = gpd.read_file(geojson_file)
    ireland_boundary = ireland_boundary.to_crs(epsg=3857)

    # Map 1: Plot points without text decorations
    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
    gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, color='red', markersize=50, alpha=0.7, label='ogham sites')
    ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
    ax.set_axis_off()
    plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites (OSM)")
    plt.legend()
    plt.show()

    # Map 2: Plot with points colored by county and fix legend
    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
    unique_counties = gdf['countyLabel'].unique()
    colors = plt.cm.tab20.colors[:len(unique_counties)] # Generate unique colors
    county_colors = {county: colors[idx] for idx, county in enumerate(unique_counties)}

    patches = []
    for county, color in county_colors.items():
        county_data = gdf_mercator[gdf_mercator['countyLabel'] == county]
        county_data.plot(ax=ax, color=color, markersize=50, alpha=0.7)
        patches.append(Patch(color=color, label=county)) # Add patch for legend

    ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
    ax.set_axis_off()
    plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties")
    plt.legend(handles=patches, title="Counties", bbox_to_anchor=(1.05, 1), loc='upper left')
    plt.show()

    # Map 3: Density map with normalized values
    x = gdf_mercator.geometry.x
    y = gdf_mercator.geometry.y

    # Calculate kernel density
    xy = np.vstack([x, y])
    kde = gaussian_kde(xy)
    density = kde(xy)

    # Normalize density to range [0, 1]
    density_normalized = (density - density.min()) / (density.max() - density.min())
    gdf_mercator['density'] = density_normalized

    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
    ireland_boundary.plot(ax=ax, color="white", edgecolor="black")
    gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, column='density', cmap="Reds", markersize=50, alpha=0.7, legend=True)
    ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
    ax.set_axis_off()
    plt.title("Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)")
    plt.show()
```


	item	itemLabel	site	siteLabel	county	countyLabel	latitude	longitude
0	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892459	CIIC 71 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85394002	Ahalisky (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.678889	-8.846944
1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892460	CIIC 72 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85394004	Aultagh (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.770833	-9.088056
2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892463	CIIC 73 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393926	Carhoovauler (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.688333	-8.956111
3	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892466	CIIC 74 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393926	Carhoovauler (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.688333	-8.956111
4	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892468	CIIC 75 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393928	Keenrath (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.759444	-9.185833
...
328	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892620	CIIC 156 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
329	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892623	CIIC 157 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
330	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892626	CIIC 158 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
331	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892629	CIIC 159 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
332	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892630	CIIC 160 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111

333 rows x 8 columns

via <https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/jupyter-nb-lod/wikidata-ogham-sites-map>

Wikidata

Map of Ogham Stone Sites (OSM)

Item [Discussion](#)

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q130529871)

Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor

Q130529871 [edit](#)

[View in more languages](#)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor	Q130529871
German	No label defined	No description defined	
French	No label defined	No description defined	
Bavarian	No label defined	No description defined	

All entered languages

Statements

Instance of

- ogham stone [edit](#)
 - 0 references [+ add reference](#)
- Ogham Stone Semantic Concept [edit](#)
 - 0 references [+ add reference](#)
- archaeological artifact [edit](#)
 - 0 references

Identifiers

FactGrid item ID [edit](#) Q1000294 → 0 references

Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID [edit](#) CO074-148---- → 0 references

OpenStreetMap node ID [edit](#) 11071361392 → 0 references

Wikidata [Q130529871]

Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)

Main page
Recent changes
Random page
Help about MediaWiki

Wikibase
New item
New property
New schema
List properties
Query service

Tools
What links here
Related changes
Upload file
Special pages
Printable version
Permanent link
Page information
Concept URI

In other languages
Add links

Item Discussion

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV (Q1247)

3D model of the Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor

edit

In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	3D model of the Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor	
British English	No label defined	No description defined	

Mapping to other ontologies

Predicate	URL	
		+ add mapping

Statements

instance of Media item edit

0 references + add reference

+ add value

license Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike edit

0 references + add reference

+ add value

has technique Photogrammetry edit

file view

<https://semantic-kompakkt.de/entity/670e54210da6ec51ee08e5fb>

Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV

3D model of the Ogham Stone #4 in the University College Cork Stone Corridor

Related agents

Rightsowner: [University College Cork \(UCC\)](#)

Data Creator: [Anne-Karoline Distel](#)

Creator: [Anne-Karoline Distel](#)

Editor: [Florian Thierj](#)

Contact Person: [Florian Thierj](#)

Licence

[Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike 4.0 International \(CC BY-NC-SA 4.0\)](#)

Creation

Technique: [Photogrammetry](#)

Software: [KIRI engine](#)

Equipment: Smartphone

Date: Invalid Date

Related object structure

[Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV](#)

cassittas (Q1013406)

a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	cassittas	a person mentioned in an inscription on an Ogham Stone

Item Discussion

C[A]SSITT[A]S Annotation (CIIC 81) (Q1255)

Person in C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUQOI CALLITI

▼ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	C[A]SSITT[A]S Annotation (CIIC 81)	Person in C[A]SSITT[A]S MAQI MUQOI CALLITI

Main page
Recent changes
Random page
Help about MediaWiki

Wikibase
New item

Semantic Kompakt [Q1247]

THX to
Lozana !!!

Federating between *Semantic Kompakkt* to get the 3D file view location & *Wikidata* to get all external IDs

Wikibase / Query Service Examples

Query Helper

+ Filter

object of representation

+ Show

file view

wikidata id

Limit

[Query source](#)

```
1 PREFIX wd: <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/>
2 PREFIX wdt: <http://www.wikidata.org/prop/direct/>
3 PREFIX wdqs: <https://query.wikidata.org/sparql>
4
5 SELECT DISTINCT ?CIIC81Label ?3D_view ?wd_id ?OSM_id ?SMRS_id ?LOD_id ?Factgrid_id WHERE {
6   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "[AUTO_LANGUAGE],en". }
7   VALUES ?CIIC81 {tib:Q1407}
8   ?Media_item tibt:P63 ?CIIC81.
9   ?Media_item tibt:P74 ?3D_view.
10  ?CIIC81 tibt:P107 ?wd_id.
11
12  BIND(IRI(CONCAT(STR(wd:), ?wd_id)) AS ?wd_item)
13
14  SERVICE wdqs: {
15    ?wd_item wdt:P11693 ?OSM_id;
16    wdt:P4057 ?SMRS_id;
17    wdt:P2888 ?LOD_id;
18    wdt:P8168 ?Factgrid_id.
19  }
20 }
21
```

1 result in 513 ms

CIIC81Label	3D_view	wd_id	OSM_id	SMRS_id	LOD_id	Factgrid_id
Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV	https://semantic-kompakkt.de/entity/670e542110da6ec51ee08e5fb	Q130529871	11071361392	CO074-148----	http://lod.ogham.link/data/Y50000081	Q1000294

DIAS
 Institiúid Ard-Léinn | Dublin Institute for
 Bhaile Átha Cliath | Advanced Studies

The Discovery Programme
 Centre for Archaeology
 and Innovation Ireland

An Roinn Cultúir,
 Oidhreacht agus Gaeltachta
 Department of Culture,
 Heritage and the Gaeltacht

museum
 National Museum of Ireland
 Ard-Mhúsaem na hÉireann

OGHAM IN 3D

<https://ogham.celt.dias.ie>

Das Ogham in 3D und OG(H)AM Projekt scannt Ogham Steine ...

CIIC 187

- **Kilmalkedar Church (Cill Maoilchéadair)**
- **OSM: node/9110402648**
- **Wikidata: Q70892706**
- **O3D: 187._Kilmalkedar**
- **SMR: KE052-059002-**

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

**Knoten: CIIC 187
(9110402648)**

Version #5

small fixes

Bearbeitet vor 20 Tagen von fthierrygo
Änderungssatz #12563590
Standort: 52.1847478, -10.3364628

Tags

historic	ogham_stone
image	https://www.flickr.com/photos/196367420@N05/52324823400/ n/album-72177720301745883/
inscription	ANM MAILE-INBIR MACI BROCANN
name	CIIC 187
project	ogham.link
source	https://hollywellscocke.ndkerry.com/2019/08/21/two-wells-a-whole-lot-more-at-cill-mhaoilcheadair/survey
wikidata	Q70892706

Item **Discussion**

Cill Maoilchéadair | Kilmalkedar (I-KER-055) (Q49)

No description defined
CIIC 187

▼ In more languages
Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	Cill Maoilchéadair Kilmalkedar (I-KER-055)	No description defined
German	No label defined	No description defined
American English	No label defined	No description defined
default for all languages	No label defined	—

Statements

instance of	Object	▼ 0 references
OSM ID	node/9110402648	▼ 0 references
representative point	52°11'5.0921"N, 10°20'11.2661"W	▼ 0 references

aligned with term

<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q2016147>

alignment label	Ogham Stone
alignment type (SKOS)	skos:exactMatch
alignment score	7 Star
alignment repository	Wikidata
alignment description	object type
alignment source	OSM

▼ 0 references

<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q55046509>

alignment label	Kilmalkedar Church
alignment type (SKOS)	skos:relatedMatch
alignment score	3 Star
alignment repository	Wikidata
alignment description	exhibition
alignment source	OSM

▼ 0 references

- Main page
- Recent changes
- Random page
- Help about MediaWiki

Tools

- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
- Printable version
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Concept URI

Wikibase

- New Item
- New Property
- New Schema
- All Properties
- Query Service
- Cradle
- QuickStatements

In other languages

✚ Add links

I-KER-055 in der SquirrelBase I

Sketchfab URL

<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/kilmalkedar-ogham-stone-rgb-27a2344de48842978505db558cc0712c>

acquisition method	Laser Scan
acquisition hardware	Artec Eva scanner, Faro scanner
acquisition software	Geomagic
acquisition creator	Rob Shaq, Discovery Programme
acquisition license	CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 Ireland

▼ 0 references

3D File URL

https://ogham.celt.dias.ie/version2013/stone.php?lang=en&site=Kilmalkedar&stone=187._Kilmalkedar&stoneinfo=inscription

acquisition method	Laser Scan
acquisition hardware	Artec Eva scanner, Faro scanner
acquisition software	Geomagic
acquisition creator	Rob Shaq, Discovery Programme
acquisition license	CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 Ireland

▼ 0 references

I-KER-055 in der SquirrelBase II

CIIC 242

- **Aghadoe Church (Ruine)**
- **OSM: [node/10040757680](#)**
- **Wikidata: [Q70892852](#)**
- **O3D: 242._Parkavonear**
- **SMR: KE066-016009-**

Open Street Map Contributors, ODbL

Knoten: CIIC 242
(10040757680)

Version #3

add SMR number

Bearbeitet vor einer Minute von fthieryego

Änderungssatz #133566349

Standort: 52,0767683, -9,5543233

Tags

historic	ogham_stone
inscription	BRRUANANN
moved	no
name	CIIC 242
project	ogham.link
ref:ESmr	KE066-016009-
source	survey
wikidata	Q70892852

Ogham in 3D (O3D) [Inscriptions](#) [About](#) [Bibliography](#)

Páirc an Mhóinéir | Parkavonear 1 (I-KER-112)

CIIC 242

[← Previous](#)

[Next →](#)

PROVENANCE

Discovery: 1804 Pelham (3 fragments cemented together)

Findspot: Parkavonear (Páirc an Mhóinéir <https://www.logainm.ie/en/231731>), Co. Kerry, Ireland (TM coordinates: 493429, 592732)

Last recorded location(s): in situ (cemented to top of the S wall of the chancel of Aghadoo church)

SUPPORT

[National Monuments Service](#) SMR ID: KEG66-016005-

Object type: Pillar

Dimensions:

Letters:

EDITION

[Interpretive](#) [Diplomatic](#)

BRUANANN

Critical Apparatus

TRANSLATION

COMMENTARY

REFERENCES

[Maxwell 1945...](#)

UK Research and Innovation

Toighde Éireann Research Ireland

DIAS

Katherine Forsyth, Deborah Hayden, Megan Kasen, Patricia O' Connors, David Siffes, Nora White. Ogham in 3D, v.2.0 (2023). Dublin Institute for Advanced Studies. <https://ogham.celt.dias.ie>

I-KER-112 im OG(H)AM Projekt

- Main page
- Recent changes
- Random page
- Help about MediaWiki

Tools

- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
- Printable version
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Concept URI

Wikibase

- New Item
- New Property
- New Schema
- All Properties
- Query Service
- Cradle
- QuickStatements

In other languages

[Add links](#)

Item **Discussion**

Páirc an Mhóinéir | Parkavonear 1 (I-KER-112) (Q50)

No description defined
 ClIC 242

▼ In more languages
 Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	Páirc an Mhóinéir Parkavonear 1 (I-KER-112)	No description defined	ClIC 242
German	No label defined	No description defined	
American English	No label defined	No description defined	
default for all languages	No label defined	—	

Statements

instance of	Object	▼ 0 references
OSM ID	node/10040757680	▼ 0 references
representative point	52°4'36.3659"N, 9°33'15.5639"W	▼ 0 references

<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q2016147>

alignment label	Ogham Stone
alignment type (SKOS)	skos:exactMatch
alignment score	7 Star
alignment repository	Wikidata
alignment description	object type
alignment source	OSM

▼ 0 references

<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q30247109>

alignment label	Aghadoe Early Medieval Ecclesiastical Site
alignment type (SKOS)	skos:relatedMatch
alignment score	3 Star
alignment repository	Wikidata
alignment description	exhibition
alignment source	OSM

▼ 0 references

I-KER-112 in der SquirrelBase I

Sketchfab URL

<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/parkavonear-ogham-stone-4a214a15d68e46d3ae985bcb528b3e02>

acquisition method	Laser Scan
acquisition hardware	Artec Eva scanner
acquisition software	Geomagic
acquisition creator	Gary Devlin, Discovery Programme
acquisition license	CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 Ireland

▼ 0 references

3D File URL

https://ogham.celt.dias.ie/version2013/stone.php?lang=en&site=Parkavonear&stone=242._Parkavonear&stoneinfo=inscription

acquisition method	Laser Scan
acquisition hardware	Artec Eva scanner
acquisition software	Geomagic
acquisition creator	Gary Devlin, Discovery Programme
acquisition license	CC BY-NC-SA 3.0 Ireland

▼ 0 references

I-KER-112 in der SquirrelBase II

Irish Holy Wells

3D-Modelle in der LOD Cloud

b-unicycling, CC BY 4.0, via <https://skfb.ly/oWvIB>

Anne-Karoline Distel, CC0, via Wikimedia Commons

Freshford: St Lachtain's Well

via <http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q121840779>

St. Lachtain's Well (Q121840779)

Label: **St. Lachtain's Well** (English) | Description: **Holy well dedicated to St. Lachtain near Freshford, Co. Kilkenny** | Also known as: **St. Lachtain's Well** (English), **St. Lachtain's Well** (Irish), **Tobertachain** (Irish)

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
English	St. Lachtain's Well	Holy well dedicated to St. Lachtain near Freshford, Co. Kilkenny	St. Lachtain's Well Tobertachain
German	No label defined	No description defined	
French	No label defined	No description defined	
Basenian	No label defined	No description defined	

All other languages

Statements

- instance of**
 - Holy Well **Wikimedia Commons** **0** references
 - Spring **3** references
 - Holy well **1** reference
 - site of use **1** reference
 - architectural structure **0** references
- image**
 - Tobertachain - Saint Lachtain 02.jpg **0** references
- significant person**
 - William Kissella **1** reference
- named after**
 - Lachtain mac Taidin **0** references
- country**
 - Ireland **0** references
- located in the administrative territorial entity**
 - County Kilkenny **0** references
 - Freshford **0** references

Identifiers

Irish Sites and Monuments Record ID **KK013-025----** **1** reference

OpenStreetMap way ID **935503837** **0** references

Wiki Loves Monuments ID **IE-KK-0248** **0** references

OpenStreetMap **Way: Saint Lachtain's Well (935503837)** **Version #8**

ref: iD user requires her/his/it/2
 Edited 11 months ago by geonovig
 Changed 4 #1215336

Tags

alt_name	Tobertachain
amenity	place_of_worship
class_date	0133-06-23
denomination	roman_catholic
description	Walled enclosure with wrought iron gate. Stone paved ground with subcircular water basin which is covered in water tanks.
heritage	2
heritage:operator	IE:swr
name	Tobertachain
name:en	Saint Lachtain's Well
name:en:etymology:wikid	
id	Q11674003
name:ga	Tobertachain
natural	spring
place_of_worship	holy_well
ref:swr	KK013-025
religion	catholic
source	British War Office maps:swr
survey:date	2021-05-26
upload:tab	https://sfb.ly/ow/8
water	spring
wikidata	Q121840779
wikimedia_commons	Category:Tobertachain

Nodes **11** nodes

via <https://www.openstreetmap.org/way/935503837>

Freshford: St Lachtain's Well

Item [Discussion](#)

St. Lachtain's Well (Q27)

object

[In more languages](#)

[Configure](#)

Language	Label	Description
English	St. Lachtain's Well	object
German	No label defined	No description defined
American English	No label defined	No description defined
default for all languages	No label defined	—

Statements

instance of	Object	0 references
Wikidata Q-ID	Q121840779	0 references
OSM ID	way/935503837	0 references
representative point	52°43′53.746″N, 7°23′22.236″W	0 references

aligned with term

<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1371047>

alignment label	Holy Well
alignment type (SKOS)	skos:exactMatch
alignment score	7 Star
alignment repository	Wikidata
alignment description	object type
alignment source	Pádraig Ó Dálaigh: The holy wells of County Kilkenny II

[0 references](#)

<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q60554307>

alignment label	Freshford
alignment type (SKOS)	skos:relatedMatch
alignment score	3 Star
alignment repository	Wikidata
alignment description	civil parish in County Kilkenny, Ireland
alignment source	Wikidata (Q121840779)

[0 references](#)

St Lachtain's Well in der SquirrelBase I

Sketchfab URL

<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/freshford-st-lachtains-well-low-poly-ae1e1f4daa7d433dbbf076407134e81e>

acquisition method	Structure from Motion (SfM)
acquisition hardware	iPhone
acquisition software	KIRI engine
acquisition creator	Anne-Karoline Distel
acquisition license	CC BY 4.0

▼ 0 references

St Lachtain's Well in der SquirrelBase II

Govan Stones

3D-Modelle in der LOD Cloud

6.2 Govan 2

The hogbacks of Govan have been the subject of intense study since James Lang's original consideration of the Scottish hogbacks (1974); scholarly interest in this monument type has only increased since (Lang 1984; Lang 1994; Ritchie 2004; Crawford 2005; Williams 2015; Whitworth 2016; Barnes 2019). Govan 2 (Lang 1, ECMS 2), is one of the best preserved of the Govan hogbacks. A band of a variety of median-incised motifs has been carved along the bottom of the monument; while the art historical similarities with the Irish sea and Cumbria have been considered in previous discussion of these motifs (Lang 1994, 125), but it is also worth noting that the ring-chain utilised in the band is very similar to that found elsewhere in the Govan collection on Govan 24 (see Section 6.16 below). Above this band, two rows of concave tiles have been carved on each side. A small panel survives on one of the short edges of the monument, which has been decorated with a swastika motif. Two small panels of step pattern flank this panel. Two weathered beast heads remain, one on each short face of the monument. The ridge of Govan 2, however, is significantly worn. The digital three-dimensional model of the stone revealed that at least one side of the ridge had been previously decorated with step pattern, which has not been commented on previously (Figure 6.2). The identification of this pattern has recently been confirmed by John Borland, who has been illustrating the corpus of Govan monuments.

<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/govan-2-b9dc56bfc1d342f6b4da3281e6629c07>

Florian Thiery, CC BY 4.0

Figure 6.2. Faint remnants of step pattern can be seen on the ridge of Govan 2, above the uppermost row of tile-pattern.

Kasten, Megan Nichole. 2019. 'The Govan Stones Revealed: Digital Imaging in the Analysis of Early Medieval Sculpture'. Doctoral Thesis (PhD), University of Glasgow.
<https://doi.org/10.5525/gla.thesis.74266>.

Hogback Govan Stone 2 @ Govan Old Parish Church, Glasgow, Scotland

Govan Stone 02 (Hogback)

Govan 2 (in both Stirling Maxwell's and ECMS numbering; Lang 1) is one of the smallest of Govan's five hogbacks and is the best preserved.

[Related agents](#)

[Creation](#)

[External Links](#)

[Related object structure](#)

Hogback Govan Stone 2 @ **Semantic Kompakt** (by M.N. Kasten)

- Main page
- Recent changes
- Random page
- Help about MediaWiki

- Wikibase
- New item
- New property
- New schema
- List properties
- Query service

- Tools
- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
- Printable version
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Concept URI

Item **Discussion**

Govan Stone o2 (Hogback) (Q1772)

Archaeological Artifact

↳ In more languages
Configure

Language	Label	Description
British English	No label defined	No description defined
English	Govan Stone O2 (Hogback)	Archaeological Artifact

↳ Mapping to other ontologies

Predicate	URL
-----------	-----

Statements

instance of **Human-Made Object**
↳ 0 references

Wikidata id **Q136659904**
↳ 0 references

- Main page
- Recent changes
- Random page
- Help about MediaWiki
- Wikibase
- New item
- New property
- New schema
- List properties
- Query service

- Tools
- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
- Printable version
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Concept URI

Item **Discussion**

Govan Stone o2 (Hogback) (Q1773)

Govan 2 (in both Stirling Maxwell's and ECMS numbering; Lang 1) is one of the smallest of Govan's five hogbacks

↳ In more languages
Configure

Language	Label	Description
British English	No label defined	No description defined
English	Govan Stone O2 (Hogback)	Govan 2 (in both Stirling Maxwell's and ECMS numbering; Lang 1) is one of the smallest of Govan's five hogbacks and is the best preserved.

↳ Mapping to other ontologies

Predicate	URL
-----------	-----

Statements

instance of **Media item**
↳ 0 references

license **Creative Commons Attribution**
↳ 0 references

method **Photogrammetry**
↳ 0 references

software **Agisoft Metashape**
↳ 0 references

ZBrush
↳ 0 references

object of representation **Ogham Stone UCC Stone Corridor IV**
↳ 0 references

file view **<https://semantic-kompakt.de/entity/6900db0ab8796a7fba84f05>**
↳ 0 references

external link **<https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/govan-2-b9dc56bfc1d342f6b4da3281e6629c07>**
↳ 0 references

right held by **Megan Nichole Kasten**
↳ 0 references

contact person **Florian Thier**
↳ 0 references

created by (event) **Creation**
carried out by **Megan Nichole Kasten**
↳ 0 references

Hogback Govan Stone 2 @ Semantic Kompakt Wikibase

Govan Stone 02 (Museum Item)

Hogback at Govan Church in Glasgow

Related agents

Rightsowner: [Florian.Thiery](#)

Creator: [Florian.Thiery](#)

Contact Person: [Florian.Thiery](#)

Creation

Technique: [Photogrammetry](#)

Software: [KIRI.engine](#)

Hogback Govan Stone 2 @ **Semantic Kompakkt** (made with KIRI Engine)

- Main page
- Recent changes
- Random page
- Help about MediaWiki

Wikibase

- New item
- New property
- New schema
- List properties
- Query service

Tools

- What links here
- Related changes
- Special pages
- Printable version
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Concept URI

Item **Discussion**

Govan Stone 02 (Hogback) (Q1772)

Archaeological Artifact

▾ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
British English	No label defined	No description defined
English	Govan Stone 02 (Hogback)	Archaeological Artifact

▸ Mapping to other ontologies

Predicate	URL
-----------	-----

Statements

instance of	Human-Made Object
	▾ 0 references

Wikidata id	Q136659904
	▾ 0 references

- Main page
- Recent changes
- Random page
- Help about MediaWiki

Wikibase

- New item
- New property
- New schema
- List properties
- Query service

Tools

- What links here
- Related changes
- Upload file
- Special pages
- Printable version
- Permanent link
- Page information
- Concept URI

Item **Discussion**

Govan Stone 02 (Museum Item) (Q1775)

Hogback at Govan Church in Glasgow

▾ In more languages

Configure

Language	Label	Description
English	Govan Stone 02 (Museum Item)	Hogback at Govan Church in Glasgow
British English	No label defined	No description defined

▸ Mapping to other ontologies

Predicate	URL
-----------	-----

Statements

instance of	Media item
	▾ 0 references

license	Creative Commons Attribution
	▾ 0 references

method	Photogrammetry
--------	----------------

Hogback Govan Stone 2 @ Semantic Kompakkt Wikibase

Main page
Recent changes
Random page
Help about MediaWiki

Tools
What links here
Related changes
Special pages
Printable version
Permanent link
Page information
Concept URI

Wikibase

New Item
New Property
New Schema
All Properties
Query Service
Cradle
QuickStatements

In other languages
[Add links](#)

Item [Discussion](#)

Govan Stone 02 (Hogback) (Q51)

No description defined

[In more languages](#)

[Configure](#)

Language	Label	Description
English	Govan Stone 02 (Hogback)	No description defined
German	No label defined	No description defined
American English	No label defined	No description defined
default for all languages	No label defined	–

Statements

instance of	Object	0 references
Wikidata Q-ID	Q136659904	0 references
OSM ID	node/12920194973	0 references
representative point	55°51′52.3692″N, 4°18′46.6960″W	0 references

aligned with term

<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q1570646>

alignment label	Hogback
alignment type (SKOS)	skos:exactMatch
alignment score	7 Star
alignment repository	Wikidata
alignment description	object type
alignment source	Wikidata

[0 references](#)

<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q42887850>

alignment label	The Govan Stones
alignment type (SKOS)	skos:closeMatch
alignment score	6 Star
alignment repository	Wikidata
alignment description	collection
alignment source	Wikidata

[0 references](#)

<http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q5588564>

alignment label	Govan Old Parish Church
alignment type (SKOS)	skos:relatedMatch
alignment score	3 Star
alignment repository	Wikidata
alignment description	stone is within church
alignment source	Wikidata

[0 references](#)

Hogback Govan Stone 2 in der SquirrelBase I

Sketchfab URL	https://sketchfab.com/3d-models/govan-2-b9dc56bfc1d342f6b4da3281e6629c07	
	acquisition method	Structure from Motion (SfM)
	acquisition hardware	Nikon D5300, Nikon D5500, Samsung Galaxy A3 (8MP), ReTrak EUselfieB Bluetooth Selfie Stick
	acquisition software	Agisoft PhotoScan
	acquisition creator	Megan Nicole Kasten
	acquisition license	CC BY 4.0
	▼ 0 references	

Semantic Kompakkt URL	https://semantic-kompakkt.de/entity/6900db0bab8796a7fba64f05	
	acquisition method	Structure from Motion (SfM)
	acquisition hardware	Nikon D5300, Nikon D5500, Samsung Galaxy A3 (8MP), ReTrak EUselfieB Bluetooth Selfie Stick
	acquisition software	Agisoft PhotoScan
	acquisition creator	Megan Nicole Kasten
	acquisition license	CC BY 4.0
	▼ 0 references	
	https://semantic-kompakkt.de/entity/6908819cdf9a1290826f9d51	
acquisition method	Structure from Motion (SfM)	
acquisition hardware	Samsung Galaxy S22	
acquisition software	KIRI engine	
acquisition creator	Florian Thiery	
acquisition license	CC BY 4.0	
▼ 0 references		

Hogback Govan Stone 2 in der SquirrelBase II

Finis! Thx! Questions?

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